

THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NOVEL GENRE IN ENGLISH LITERATURE

Xolmuradova Madina

Karshi State University

Graduate Department

Master's student in Linguistics (English)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10976678>

Annotation: In world literature, views on the science of novel genre and theory of forms are constantly updated and developed. Thoughts about this are often expressed syncretically in historical and biographical works in Eastern classical literature. In particular, in today's era of globalization, the study of the literature and culture of a certain period on the example of the works of individual creators, the tradition and innovation manifested in their work, the uniqueness of genres and forms, individual style and skill, man and era, historical truth and artistic image and so on is gaining importance in the study of theoretical issues.

Keywords: poetry, lyrical, period, genre, literature, novel, drama, poet.

In the 18th century, Britain was as important as France. This redounded from the growth of its diligence and from the wealth of its large new trading conglomerate. Britain had the strongest cortege in the world, the cortege was controlled Britain's own trade routes and risked those of its adversaries. Britain came fat thanks to trade. This wealth made possible both an agrarian and an artificial revolution which made Britain the most advanced frugality in the world.

The second period of the Enlightenment was the most mature: the forties and the fifties of the 18th century. It saw the development of the realistic social novel represented by Richardson, Fielding, and Smollett.

The third period refers to the last decades of the century. It is marked by the appearance of a new trend: Sentimentalism. The representatives of this trend were Goldsmith and Sterne. This period also saw the rise of realistic drama (Sheridan) and the revival of poetry.

European literature of the 18th century refers to literature (poetry, drama, satire, essays, and novels) produced in Europe during this period. The 18th century saw the development of the modern novel as literary genre, in fact many candidates for the first novel in English date from this period, of which Daniel Defoe's *Robinson Crusoe* is probably the best known. Subgenres of the novel during the 18th century were the epistolary novel, the sentimental novel, histories, the gothic novel and the libertine novel.

Starting in the 18th century, the epistolary form was subject to much ridicule, resulting in many savage burlesques. The most notable example of these was Henry Fielding's *Shamela* (1741), written as a parody of *Pamela*. In it, the female narrator can be found wielding a pen and scribbling her diary entries under the most dramatic and unlikely of circumstances. Oliver Goldsmith used the form to satirical effect in *The Citizen of the World*, subtitled "Letters from a Chinese Philosopher Residing in London to his Friends in the East" (1760–61). So did the diarist Fanny Burney in a successful comic first novel, *Evelina* (1788).

The epistolary novel slowly became less popular after the 18th century. Although Jane Austen tried the epistolary in juvenile writings and her novella *Lady Susan* (1794), she abandoned this structure for her later work. It is thought that her lost novel *First Impressions*, which was

redrafted to become *Pride and Prejudice*, may have been epistolary: *Pride and Prejudice* contains an unusual number of letters quoted in full and some play a critical role in the plot.

Evolution of the Novel in the 21st century, where the novel is quite possibly the most popular form of literature, it is hard for one to believe that its form is relatively novel for the world. Before the 18th century, there were no known literary pieces in existence that fit the definition of a "novel" (refer to the above section for definition). Before discussing the novel itself, it is important to examine its evolution. Traditionalism in literature was a key to success before the latter half of the eighteenth century. Authors such as Milton, who wrote *Paradise Lost*, were responsible for telling stories in which the people were familiar. The fiction that was produced before the introduction and development of the novel was never based on actual people but on characters whom everyone was familiar with, Hercules, Adam and Eve, etc. Thus, the success of an author was mainly based on whether or not he could re-invent an already popular story and model the traditional classics from the days of year.

Novel as a literary genre enjoyed the highest level of glory in the 18th century. The authors namely Defoe, Richardson, Fielding and Sterne contributed significantly to the development of English novel. They influenced the writers who came after them. The 18th century coincided with the industrial revolution which significantly contributed to the rise of the novel (with the invention of printing machine). The chain effects of industrial revolution improved people's life and living standard. The rise of the educated middle-class people further increased the reading public which correspondingly led to demand of novels for reading. Books such as 'Don Quixote', 'Decameron', 'Morte d' Arthur' and 'Pilgrim's Progress' laid the foundations for the development of the novel. 'Pamela', 'Joseph Andrew's', 'Tristram Shandy', and 'Robinson Crusoe' were some of the notable books that became famous in the 18th century. However, novels continued to evolve in the 19th and 20th century giving rise to different genres or classes of novel.

Literature is a criterion that expresses the national spirit of the most developed peoples in the world in terms of the fact that it has been able to preserve the national spirit and has been able to rise to a large scale in the variety of artistic images and styles. English literature has its own characteristics, which arise from the uniqueness of the country's culture, social and political development. It corresponds to the XIX century, defined the problems of literature and its forms. English writers, first of all, the novel develops at this stage, looked for their heroes not among bankers, aristocrats, but among those who sought to gain a career, as in France - their heroes were also small owners, like J. Eliot ("The Mill on the Floss"), even workers such as E. Gaskell ("Mary Barton") or Charles Dickens ("Hard Times"). Indeed, under the mask of calmness, a weak person may be hiding, filled with the desire to appear strong and invulnerable. External objectivity is characteristic of gentlemen in literature (Pickwick, Forestier, Worcester, etc.), as well as characters who keep secrets. Many characters express themselves with humor, and often in serious works there is a funny character with a bright, complex speech. You will never confuse Bertie Worcester with any other funny characters. Dickens's hero, Sam Weller, is the epitome of people who love aphorisms. In English literature, there is a belief that the English have a more refined and developed sense of humor than other nations, that other nations think prosaically and do not understand or appreciate irony, which in the words of Keith Fox "When they are joking or serious you don't know at all". In particular, the types of English humor include the technique of "cotton", which,

according to Keith Fox, is a form of irony, the essence of which is excessive seriousness, sentimentality, boasting and insistence on showing one's feeling is a prohibition. The English are also famous for their ability to laugh at themselves, which is the most important sign of a mature civilization. To understand and get the overview of the rise of the novel in 18th century, one needs to trace back to the origin as well as look ahead or even beyond the 18th century. This is because of the fact that the readers are already in the 21st century. It becomes necessary to get overall understanding of how the development of novels started and evolved in the process to reach the present form. However, due to the extensive nature of the topic, many notable authors and novels despite being important are being left out. Therefore, it is important that one take the ideas from this paper and explore further to enrich one's understanding of the development and rise of English novels.

References:

1. Albert, E. (1979). History of English literature (5th ed. New Delhi: Oxford University Press.
2. Amin, M.A. (2012). The English romantic movement "as return to nature. Or, the main features of romanticism.
3. Bora, M. (n. d). Back ground to the rise of the novel.
4. Hasan, M.N. (2015). The eighteenth century and the rise of the English novel. International Journal of Literature and Art, 3 (2), 18-21. Doi: 10.11648/j.ijla.20150302.12
5. qizi Zarifova, D. O. (2023). SHARQ GRAFIKA SAN'ATIDA MAISHIY JANRNING O'RGANILISHI. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(9), 57-62.
6. Kettle, A. (1967). An introduction to the English novel. New Delhi: Universal Book Stall.

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY